

R-TIK Digital Transformation towards Indonesia Information Society

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ABSTRACT: As a developing country, Indonesians are still constrained by the use of digital-based technology. Based on the characteristics of geographic areas, digital discrepancy becomes an inevitable problem. So that in order to create an Information Society according to the agreement of the World Summit on the Information Society (WSIS), collaboration between various parties is needed. One of the efforts made by the Indonesian government is to encourage the formation of the Information Society through the policy of forming Information and Communication Technology Volunteers (in Indonesia known as R-TIK/Indonesia ICT Volunteers) in various regions spread throughout Indonesia. This study aims to determine the activities of R-TIK in realizing the Information Society in Indonesia. The method used is descriptive qualitative, by conducting in-depth observations and participant observation with R-TIK activists, stakeholders, business actors (UMKM/SMMEs), and the community as R-TIK partners. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that R-TIK is able to encourage public awareness in the sustainable use of digital technology. Even R-TIK together with UMKM (SMMEs) have been able to push the rate of economic growth in Indonesia by utilizing digital technology under the name Qren.

KEYWORDS: R-TIK, Digital Gap, UMKM, Information Society, Digital Technology

INTRODUCTION

Fast technological developments are sometimes difficult to anticipate in the process of community adaptation. There is a change in the exchange of information, the abundance of information that is fast and easily accessible requires quick adaptation as well. For developed countries this is not a problem because with a good education system and economy, they are able to quickly catch the progress. On the other hand, for developing countries with relatively diverse communities, opportunities in digital technology have not been maximally utilized. Indonesia as a developing country is still experiencing a digital discrepancy. Until now, there are still 12,458 or 14% of the 83,280 villages and sub-districts in Indonesia that are not connected to the 4G network (Yunianto, 2020).

In the process of exchanging information, it provides both access and utilization speed. Indonesia, as one of the countries that is part of the World Summit on the Information Society (WSIS), has also agreed to create a world Information Society, which must contribute to improving the welfare of society by utilizing information as its basis. In its development, internet users in Indonesia in early 2021 have increased to 202.6 million people (Riyanto, 2021). This shows a good development in the adoption of digital communication technology. One of the factors supporting this increase is the presence of Indonesian R-TIK (ICT Volunteers) who have been encouraged by the government since 2008. The government realizes that it is impossible to build an Information Society alone. For that, it is necessary to establish partnerships with various parties. One of the efforts made by the government is to form an R-TIK (Indonesia ICT Volunteer) organization as a government partner to create a new civilization through TIK(ICT). Initially it was formed under the name of Forum Komunikasi, Koordinasi, Kolaborasi, dan Kerjasama Komunitas TIK Level Nasional (FK5T) or the National Level Communication, Coordination, Collaboration and Community ICT Forum, which then continued by holding the National I Conference. The community must be empowered to be able to make the most of digital technology. According to (Castells, 2009), the existence of belief in God, cultural values that are believed both in the family and as a nation can encourage public awareness.

Information Society

The World Summit on the Information Society (WSIS) explained the desire and commitment to build a people-centered, inclusive and development-oriented Information Society, where everyone can create, access, use and share information and knowledge that enables individuals, communities, and nations to achieve capabilities in sustainable development and improve the quality of life (Departemen Komunikasi dan Informasi RI, 2006). Through this agreement, it is hoped that developing countries can utilize

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technology to improve their quality of life so that the development process can proceed as expected. According to Ginting (2015, 27), the goal of develop an information society is to win global competition by creatively and productively utilizing information technology (IT).

In order to build an Information Society, the potential for knowledge and Information and Communication Technology has an important role in all aspects of the nation's life. The application of ICT in various fields will support the business world to develop. (Webster, 2006), identifies that there are five criteria for defining the Information Society, namely: (1) technology, (2) economy, (3) work, (4) space, (5) culture. Furthermore, said (Fuchs, 2013), information is traditionally understood subjectively as a storage space in the human brain or objectively, information is a process of cognition, communication and cooperation (Fuchs, 2013). According to Dutton (2004, 37), progress in the field of ICT has resulted in various perspectives on what technology means to society (Mardikanto, 2010). The existence of ICT provides opportunities for the community not only for advancement in the social sector, but also in the economic sector in order to improve the welfare of life. Therefore expertise is needed in developing capabilities related to ICT, especially to support development. Apart from that, access and connectivity are also an important part of connecting networks between regions. Applications and content that suit the needs of the community continue to be developed following changes in the environment. The digital divide becomes quite a challenge in the use of ICT, therefore adequate infrastructure is needed for difficult areas.

According to Alexsander Van Deursen and Jan Van Dijk, the digital discrepancy can be described through the skill level of using the internet, namely: (1) operational skills, (2) formal skills, (3), skills in using information sharing to meet with the needs, (4) strategies in using the internet as a solution to solve problems (Deursen & Dijk, 2010). Thus, skills in using the internet are not only able to use the internet, but are more required to use information on the internet as part of finding solutions to the problems at hand. Of course, with the support of knowledge about the internet will provide reinforcement in maximizing internet use. It is very important to continue to explore so that information and ICT can contribute to the sustainable development of today's society, as well as strengthen managerial methods and techniques for organizations, government and society. (Berleur, Hercheui, & Hilty, 2010; Hilty & Hercheui, 2010; Houghton, 2010)

Community Empowerment

Furthermore, said (Mardikanto, 2010), empowerment emphasizes the ability of people, especially the weak and marginalized groups, who are close to poverty. Through empowerment it is hoped that people will become aware that they are able to: (1) have access to productive sources that enable them to increase their income and obtain the goods and services they need, (2) participate in the development process and decisions which affects them (Sunuantari, 2014). Empowerment refers to efforts to reallocate power through changes in social structures.

Empowerment will be able to run quickly if it is supported by the ability to access ICT for the community. Van Dijk said, if mental problems and material access have been resolved, then in whole or in part, the structural differences in skills and usage will become more operative (Van Dijk & Hacker, 2003). For this reason, the role of the government as a stakeholder is expected to be able to provide access to the use of ICT for the community. The ability of diverse societies is not only an obstacle but also a challenge to be able to enter a new ICT-based civilization.

It is impossible for the government to do it by themselves, they must have partnerships with various parties involved in the problem of the digital gap. Even though policies have been made, there are not many skilled personnel in the use of ICT, so various enrichments must be carried out in order to address gaps in society. In addition, information agents are also needed in various areas that are difficult to access the internet, so the government considers it necessary to form an R-TIK (ICT Volunteer) organization. This R-TIK will become the agent of change in society in realizing the Information Society.

R-TIK (Indonesia ICT Volunteers)

On its journey, R-TIK continue to develop by creating Work Programs, namely:

1. Community socialization and education, aimed at making use of ICTs for economic empowerment and improving the quality of life in the direction of Indonesian society
2. Organization and Membership, register with the Ministry of Law and Human Rights and establish regional management at the provincial and district/city levels. Including open registration and data collection
3. Strengthening the Capacity of R-TIK
4. Compilation of Competency Standards, development of training modules and debriefing for Volunteers, are carried out to strengthen the capacity of R-TIK who will enter to field study to the community
5. Develop partnerships with various parties such as government, universities and schools, private sector, ICT community, and other parties so that they can work together to be able to utilize ICT in community empowerment.

For this reason, digital skills and digital literacy are needed in overcoming the digital divide between RTIK and society. When implementing in the field, actors often use conceptual models of digital literacy. (Iordace, Marien, Baelden, 2017), In this case, RTIK needs to understand the needs of interested parties in educating and utilizing digital technology. So that digital technology can encourage community empowerment in the economic field in order to improve the quality of people's lives.

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METHOD

This study uses a descriptive method with a qualitative approach, namely to observe and provide a description or description of a situation as clearly as possible to the object under study. According to Mooney (Salim, 2006), descriptive case study research explains the phenomenon under study. Through this research, it is expected to find a number of activities carried out by R-TIK in realizing the Information Society.

To obtain data as information about the problem under study, techniques are used: participant observation, literature study, and documentation. The data analysis technique used is as stated by Miles & Huberman (Denzin & Lincoln, 2009), that data analysis consists of three interrelated sub processes, namely: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion/verification. While the data validity method uses triangulation, which is checking the data by using something outside the existing data as a comparison to the data. In this study, data checking was carried out through other data sources. This research uses data validity test with source triangulation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In order to realize an information society in the future, to support the organization practically, the Indonesian R-TIK have a mission as the basis for achieving their goals, namely:

1. Gather and foster the potential of R-TIK in an organized forum, to achieve optimal efficiency, benefits and effectiveness of activities.
2. Preparing R-TIK cadres intellectually, personally and socially as well as morally, especially in the field of ICT, as elements of the next generation of development and the nation's struggle.
3. Strive together to achieve organizational goals by formulating policies, program foundations, and activity plans in accordance with technological developments in order to participate in directing the progress of society.
4. Establish coordination, cooperation, collaboration, and communication with stakeholders and other parties in society, so that they are synergistic and mutually beneficial in utilizing ICT resources for gender-aligned sustainable development, affirmative action for minorities, technology neutral, and environmentally friendly.

Through a more operational mission, R-TIK (Indonesia ICT Volunteers) can focus more on carrying out activities to achieve organizational progress. The long-term goal of encouraging the community's self-reliant economy can be achieved by making arrangements both internally and externally in the organization. The family and voluntary principles guide the running of the RTIK organization. The role of the General Chairperson is very important because it is a role model for both the board and members. In various activities carried out by regional R-TIK, they always coordinate with the Central R-TIK often directly communicating with the head of the Central R-TIK. This is done so that all R-TIK activities in the regions are in line with the Central R-TIK. Even though it is only limited to activity reports, the Central R-TIK can monitor various progress made by people in various regions in utilizing digital technology for various activities, especially those with economic value.

To carry out all R-TIK activities, the work team is divided into 7 squads, namely: Village Squad, Campus Squad, General Squad, Student Squad, Scout Squad, Pesantren Squad, UMKM (SMMEs) Squad. Each squad is responsible for digital literacy according to its target audience. Not only digital education, but also the possibility of collaborating in various fields. Even R-TIK has conducted competency tests for vocational high school students, with the hope that students who already have certification can be accepted in the world of work according to their fields. Collaboration with several campuses that have been carried out in the form of community service, namely in an effort to encourage digital culture at the village and village levels.

Transformation of R-TIK (Indonesia ICT Volunteers) in the Information Society

The Ministry of Communication and Information Technology (Kominfo), through the Directorate General of Informatics Applications Directorate of Informatics Empowerment, has made a guidelines a directive for R-TIK in building the Information Society. The reference is intended to increase the number of people who are responsive to information, both in quality and quantity. In this case R-TIK as a secondary stakeholder whose function is to increase the population of the information community.

The steps that R-TIK must go through in develop an information society are providing ICT access, and increasing the base of RTIK in development. The activity begins by creating public awareness of the importance of ICT in improving the welfare of life. The existence of awareness will encourage curiosity using ICT. This requires basic ICT training for the community. The growing awareness will trigger the acceleration of the information society population, because with ICT the community is able to empower itself. Awareness of independence will support development goals that have been set by the government. To encourage the acceleration of the formation of an information society, R-TIK has implemented digital literacy by providing assistance to the community. Assistance is carried out in order to support development programs that have been initiated by the government. The form of activities carried out by R-TIK is through workshops or TOT (Training of Trainer) for village staff and apparatus. These activities are intended to prepare human resources as managers of village information systems in the use of village information

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system applications. With the help of R-TIK, it is hoped that the village will be more economically empowered through the use of ICT. R-TIK try to encourage public awareness of the importance of digital technology in improving people's welfare.

Another program carried out by R-TIK together with The Ministry of Communication and Information Technology (Kominfo), in this case through the Director General of Informatics Applications, is the Digital Speed Campaign Program, which is directed at job seekers, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs/UMKM), and the community. The aim of the Fast Digital Campaign is to encourage people to make maximum use of the internet to achieve their expected goals. This is done in order to provide space for discussion and sharing of various positive information. Information about culture, traditions, law, economics, and other things that are the topic of the day. In the literacy program run by R-TIK, it always refers to the needs of the surrounding community, so that it can have a direct impact on the community. In addition, the public will be more interested because the need for access to the necessary information can be fulfilled.

Since the establishment, Indonesian R-TIK have won awards at the international level three times. The first was in 2018, won the 2018 WSIS (World Summit on the Information Society) Prizes, namely in category 3 of the Goes to School (REGOS) R-TIK program initiative and in category 4 with the initiative of the Rural Information Service Center (PUSPINDES). WSIS Prizes is an annual activity carried out by the United Nations in Geneva, Switzerland through the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) organization since 2012. The second award, in 2019 R-TIK repeated their success by getting WSIS Prizes through Bojonegoro R-TIK, through Bojonegoro Data (Indonesia ICT Volunteers/R-TIK) Indonesia) is a data service, information, online library journal for the community and stakeholders in the Bojonegoro area. And the last one was in 2020, again received an award from the 2020 WSIS Prizes through the National Digital Literacy Movement (GNLD) Siberkreasi was named the winner of the WSIS C4 Capacity Building Action Lines regarding the fulfillment of SDGs Goals 4 goals, namely Quality Education.

R-TIK (Indonesia ICT Volunteers) During Covid-19 Pandemic

Even though the pandemic condition occurred, it did not receding R-TIK from providing assistance to the community in using ICT. In fact, continue to develop cooperation with various parties to achieve the main goals of R-TIK. Through the Webinar roadshow, it is hoped that assistance can still be carried out even though it is limited. Because many companies have implemented a Work from Home (WFH) policy, activities with the community can continue. The government, through the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology together with R-TIK, continues to struggle to prioritize local values in their various activities. This was done so that the program could be easily accepted by people who were not responsive to the media. The economic sector is an important thing during the Pandemic, the community must be encouraged to keep going even though it is limited. The focus of R-TIK activities is directed at:

1. Village Community Technology Transformation, namely by creating independent internet access equipped with a digital literacy movement for rural communities.
2. Digital Economy Reform, namely by creating educational and socialization programs to the public to change the mindset of society in utilizing digital technology for the recovery of the economic sector.

In order to achieve these goals, R-TIK need to collaborate with stakeholders, both government and private parties. This support is of great significance, especially in encouraging the growth of a populist economy due to the Covid-19 Pandemic. UMK (SMEs) and UMKM (SMMEs) must continue to be encouraged to move the business world. Even though it seems slow but it is giving results, some UMKM in the regions have started using digital applications to encourage promotion. In fact, the QRen application has begun to be widely used by the public as an alternative means of paying non-cash, which shows that the R-TIK (ICT Volunteers) work application is able to compete with other applications available on the Google Playstore. This is proof of the mutually beneficial cooperation between R-TIK and PT. Telkom Indonesia. The QRen platform in the future is expected to be able to create a smart business and smart city in the form of QRen Media, QRen Parking, QRen Ticketing, QRen Billing Payment. R-TIK) in its journey cannot be separated from the roles of the government and the private sector. Therefore, mutually beneficial collaboration is an alternative in digital transformation as mandated by WSIS. This is of course still prioritizing local values in the global world.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that:

1. R-TIK (ICT Volunteers) together with the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology (Kominfo) to promote the Fast Digital Campaign as an effort to encourage people to make the most of the internet and improve people's welfare economically. In its activities, R-TIK provides assistance to job seekers, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs/UMKM) actors, and other communities scattered throughout Indonesia, both offline and online.
2. In an effort to build the Indonesian Information Society, R-TIK continues to prioritize local values by developing dialogue between the community, stakeholders, and R-TIK. R-TIK and the government work together to address the digital divide in the e-government, e-business, e-learning, e-health, e-tourism, e-science, and e-environment sectors.

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3. R-TIK collaborates with PT Telkom Indonesia to provide a platform application for merchants on the Google Play Store under the name QRen. As a solution to the need for a QRIS code-based digital payment method that can be used at various types of merchants.

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